

KICHIK MAKTAB YOSH DAVRI BOLALARNING O'ZIGA XOS
XUSUSIYATLARI

Qo'qon universiteti "Ta'lim kafedrası" o'qituvchisi
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Annotation: V state formirovanie lichnosti rebenka v mladshem skolonom vozraste, uspekhi uchenika v skole yavlyayutsya positive osnovoy dlya ego dalneyshego umstvennogo razvitiya i miromovaniya ego lichnosti, v rezultate chego rebenok pminaet svoyu mestow v svoey seme, svoem klasse i other sobshchestvax. Osveshcheno, chto mojno uvidet, chto eto nachalos.

Key words: School, education, person, environment, character, vnimanie, memory, ability, rule, need.

Transition to a new activity creates a new attitude of the student to his main activity. A sense of duty begins to grow in him. He understands that studying is necessary and that it is his duty, that the established rules and requirements must be fulfilled. Feeling like a real student, he needs to read well.

The moral consciousness of students of junior school age undergoes important changes during the study of I and IV grades, and moral qualities, knowledge and imagination are significantly enriched, and the child begins to understand himself. Although he does not know his own good and bad qualities, he feels that he is "I". He realizes his duty, purpose, the need to fulfill it, and the fact that it is his duty to do homework and repeat. Children of this age are interested in learning about many environmental phenomena that are not included in the school curriculum. These interests are also reflected in the child's interest in creative games, which are often ignored. Such games reflect his social interests, emotions, concern for the team. Curiosity is a form of manifestation of broad mental activity of children of primary school age. Openness, trustworthiness, readiness to fulfill all the tasks of the teacher are the characteristics of broad social duty motives,

responsibility are effective conditions for him to know the importance and importance of studying in order to become a person needed by the country. Interests in the first years of school education, in particular, in relation to acquiring knowledge. interests, intellectual interests develop significantly. Psychologists say that first interests are formed in relation to certain facts, isolated events isolated from other things. In the III-IV grades, the interest to learn the reasons, laws, connections and interrelationships between events develops. The period of children's junior school age corresponds to the years of their studies in junior classes from 7 to 11 years old. Kindergarten childhood is over. Before coming to school, the child is physically and psychologically ready to fulfill the various district requirements for the most important period of his life, i.e. the school period. The child is clearly visible in the activities of making things out of clay or plate and in the activities of making the simplest vision. The child has gained some experience in managing his attention independently. The vocabulary of a 7-year-old child is also sufficiently rich and the number of abstract concepts is quite high. The child understands what he heard at a sufficient level. According to the research of experts, well-organized education develops the thinking of children aged 6 to 7 years. They will be able to formulate and solve simple exercises and problems. A sense of duty and responsibility is just starting to appear in them. One of the important conditions for a 7-year-old child to have the experience of managing his emotions is that he is ready for school education. When externalizing pedagogical work in small classes, it is necessary to take into account the anatomical and physiological characteristics of children of small school age and the level of social development.

D.N. As Levitov rightly noted, health status and social development at any school age is not directly related to school age. A child from 7 to 11 years of age develops relatively calmly and evenly physically. The height and weight of the organism, the vital volume of the lungs, are more flat and develop propalgitionally.

According to the psychologist L.S. Slavina, children with insufficient cognitive activity can meet in primary school.

Such children are normally developed in terms of aspirations. This development is reflected in their game and practical activities. Active thinking is characteristic for them. The teacher should pay special attention to such students. It is necessary to accustom them to the activities of their thinking and support them in all aspects of their achievements.

All learning activities of students of junior school age are necessarily coordinated with the goal. First of all, students should acquire the skills of reading, writing, and counting, and acquire a large amount of knowledge in arithmetic, mother tongue, history, geography, and natural science, rather than the elementary foundations of geometry. Secondly, the child's level of knowledge and cognitive interests expand and develop. Thirdly, the development of knowledge processes, mental development occurs. The ability for active independent creative activity is formed, and finally, the direction to study, a responsible attitude towards study, should find high factors of study. We will describe the learning processes of students of junior school age and their progress in their activities.

Perception. Children of junior school age are distinguished by the sharpness of their perception. The perception of students differs from the fact that they are given to specific knowledge as an audience.

Attention. The main features of the attention of students of junior school age are voluntary weakness. At a young school age, the ability to adjust and control attention with will power is limited.

A memory. In children of junior school age, memory develops in two directions under the influence of education. The role of the memory of the logic of the word and the meaning of the word and its importance will increase, and it will have the ability to organize.

Due to the relative predominance of the first signal system, visual-image memory is more developed in children of junior school age than the so-called

memory of word logic. Compared to rules and explanations, students of junior school age remember concrete information, realities, images, objects and facts better and keep them firmly in their memory.

Dream. Imagination is one of the important mental cognitive processes. It is impossible to truly master any educational subject without knowing how to visualize what the teacher is talking about and what is written in the lessons, and how to work with visual images without the activity of the imagination.

The imagination of a student of junior school age is formed by the influence and demands of his educational activities. In addition, direct experiences (visiting museums, museums, watching movies, going on excursions, working on the school plot, etc.) also develop the imagination.

Although the period of elementary school age is not a period of decisive changes in the development of a person, in our opinion, such a period is the period of adolescence, nevertheless, in this period, the formation of a person takes place quite significantly. As mentioned above, entering school is a turning point in a child's life. New relationships with adults (teachers) and peers (classmates) appear. The child joins the whole collective system (general school, class). Joining a new type of activity to study, where the teacher sets a number of serious requirements, forces the student to strictly externalize his life, to obey the rules and regime. All of them strongly influence the formation and strengthening of a new system of relations to the surrounding reality, to other people, to collective education and to the obligations associated with it, and to the composition of character and will. expands the range of interests, determines the development of abilities.

Mastering moral norms and rules of behavior In the period of junior school age, the foundation of moral behavior is laid, moral norms and rules of behavior are mastered. The social orientation of the individual begins to take shape. The moral consciousness of students of junior school age undergoes significant changes

during the period from the 1st to the 4th grade. By the end of this age, moral knowledge, ideas and judgments are significantly enriched, more conscious, have different concepts, generalize - moral judgments of 1st and 2nd graders are based on the experience of their behavior and teachers and based on concrete instructions and explanations of parents. 3rd-4th grade students try to analyze the experiences of other people based on the experience of their behavior and the instructions of adults in their moral judgments. When reading such literature, watching movies released for children is of great importance

Moral behavior has the same content. 7-8-year-old children do not wait for positive instructions directly from adults, including the teacher's instructions, but from the beginning they carry out such positive moral work on their own initiative.

Character. Behavioral behaviors that are manifested in children of small school age are not always stable and stable forms of behavior in which relationships are implemented. In children of junior school age, the character begins to form seriously. The character and behavior of children of junior school age can differ in their instability and contradiction. In this regard, sometimes the transient mental states in them can be attributed to the behavior of a mistake. N.D. Letovitov gives an example of this mistake. The 1st grade teacher considered one of her students to be a tenacious girl who can finish any work and overcome difficulties. However, from the observation made by an experienced psychologist, it became clear that this feature is a temporary, that is, a transient mental state that appears only under certain conditions. The failure that appeared when the student saw the behavior of the girl and the success of her friend made the girl lose track.

Interests. In the first years of school education, interests, in particular, interest in knowledge, interest in knowing the surrounding world, thirst for more knowledge and intellectual curiosity develop very significantly. According to psychologists, first of all, there is an interest in some facts, isolated events isolated from other things. After that, the interest to find out the causes, laws, connections and interrelationships between the phenomena develops. If you ask 1-2 graders

"what is this?" "why" and "how?" for older children. the questions remain external. With the development of reading skills, there will be an interest in reading books, reading certain interesting literature, fairy tales, and even more so, reading science fiction and adventure books that are not difficult. Interest in technology, especially modern technology, rockets, lunar stations, spaceships, the latest types of cars and airplanes, is rapidly developing. Pupils of 3rd-4th grade of rural schools begin to show their interest in agriculture. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the laws of the development of interests of the teacher in his relationship with the students of junior school age. As mentioned above, it is very important to feel the success of the child in his studies, which is determined by the appropriate assessment of the teacher.

Artistic and aesthetic development. In the period of junior school age, children have great opportunities for artistic and aesthetic development. Children are usually very interested in drawing, making things out of clay or plasticine, singing and music. Proper study of such activities helps children to develop aesthetic feelings on the one hand, and creates conditions for the development of the corresponding skill components on the other hand.

In conclusion, it can be said that work has a great educational value for children of primary school age. However, it should be noted that not all work can cultivate socially valuable qualities in a person. Work also educates a selfish person who is willing to work hard for his own benefit.

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